

OPTIMIZING PAIN MANAGEMENT AFTER PEDIATRIC SPINAL FUSION SURGERY: THE ROLE OF MULTIMODAL ANALGESIA

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Introduction: Scoliosis is the most prevalent spinal deformity in children, treated through conservative or surgical means. Surgical correction of scoliosis constitutes a complex procedure known for its significant postoperative pain necessitating effective analgesia.

Objective: This study aims to underscore the importance of a multimodal approach in managing postoperative pain and to illustrate the application of analgesics in treating postoperative pain following corrective surgeries for scoliosis in children.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective clinical study was conducted at the Department of Pediatric Surgery in Novi Sad, encompassing all patients operated on between February 2020 and February 2023. The research has been approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute for Child and Youth Health Care of Vojvodina.

Results: The study involved 31 patients aged 8 to 18 years, predominantly females, with an average body weight of 50.48 kg. Over half of the patients were classified as ASA II without significant comorbidities. Postoperative pain management primarily utilized opioid analgesics such as remifentanyl and morphine within the first 24 to 48 hours, followed by tramadol in combination with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and acetaminophen. The most severe pain, as measured by the VAS scale (0-10), occurred immediately postoperatively, peaking at 2 to 4 hours and 8 to 12 hours, yet generally remained mild to moderate (up to 2.5 on the VAS scale). The average stay in the intensive care unit was 2.4 days, with a total hospitalization period averaging 9.48 days.

Conclusion: Surgical correction of scoliosis results in substantial postoperative pain. Employing a multimodal approach to pain management, including opioids, facilitates more effective recovery and enhances quality of life.

Keywords: Scoliosis, postoperative pain management, opioids.